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HEPATIC STEATOSIS AND PREVALENCE OF NCDs IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING BARIATRIC SURGERY IN A REFERENCE SERVICE IN SÃO LUÍS-MA

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ABSTRACT

Bariatric surgery and lifestyle changes are an effective method to facilitate weight loss, in addition to improving comorbidities in obese patients. This study aims to correlate hepatic steatosis with the prevalence of NCDs in patients undergoing bariatric surgery. Cross-sectional study with consultation of the database of patients monitored by the Bariatric Surgery Service of the University Hospital of UFMA, with descriptive and analytical characteristics. Fifty-two patients with hepatic steatosis were evaluated, 92.3% female, with a mean age of 42 ± 9.4 years and a mean BMI of $46 \pm 7.6 \text{ Kg/m}^2$. Systemic Arterial Hypertension was the most prevalent (55.8%), followed by Diabetes mellitus (51.9%). It is concluded that hepatic steatosis is a risk factor for CNCDs. The study was able to achieve its objectives by correlating the prevalence of hepatic steatosis and its association with CNCD in preoperative bariatric surgery patients. FRARE, L. et al, 2021; LEEMAN, M. et al., 2020.

KEYWORDS: hepatic steatosis. CNCD. bariatric.